

Haradaea afromontana, comb. nov. (Microbotryaceae)

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Abstract. A new combination of *Microbotryum afromontanum* on *Cerastium afromontanum* in *Haradaea* is proposed.

Key words: Caryophyllaceae, *Haradaea*, *Microbotryum*, smut fungi

Recently, it has been demonstrated that the genus *Microbotryum* should be reduced only to the group of the anthericolous species (incl. *M. majus*) on Caryophyllaceae (Almaraz *et al.* 2002; Denchev *et al.* 2006; Kemler *et al.* 2006). For accommodation of the seed-destroying species of *Ustilago* on Caryophyllaceae, a new genus, *Haradaea*, was described (Denchev *et al.* 2006) uniting seven species: *H. alsineae* (G.P. Clinton & Zundel) Denchev & H.D. Shin, *H. arenariae-bryophyllae* (Vánky) Denchev & H.D. Shin, *H. duriaeana* (Tul. & C. Tul.) Denchev & H.D. Shin, *H. holostei* (de Bary) Denchev & H.D. Shin, *H. jehudana* (Zundel emend. Denchev) Denchev & H.D. Shin, *H. moenchie-manticae* (Lindtner) Denchev & H.D. Shin, and *H. nivalis* (Liro) Denchev & H.D. Shin. Additionally, *Ustilago moehringiae* Togashi & Y. Maki has also been transferred in *Haradaea*, viz. *H. moehringiae* (Togashi & Y. Maki) Denchev (Denchev *et al.* in press).

Vánky (2006: 50) described a new species of *Microbotryum*, *M. afromontanum*, on *Cerastium afromontanum* T.C.E. Fr. & Weimark (Caryophyllaceae) from Ethiopia. As this species is also a seed-destroying species on members of the Caryophyllaceae, similar in its symptoms and morphology to other species of *Haradaea*, we propose its transferal to this genus.

Haradaea afromontana (Vánky) Denchev, *comb. nov.*

Basionym: *Microbotryum afromontanum* Vánky, *Mycotaxon* 95: 50, 2006.

For its description and illustrations see Vánky (l.c.).

In the article establishing *Haradaea* (Denchev *et al.* 2006), the results of Almaraz *et al.* (2006), based on ITS rDNA, were taken into consideration and cited. After the publication of *Haradaea*, however, it was learned that the sequences that they reported as being from *Ustilago duriaeana* were, in fact, those of *Cryptococcus* spp. due to contamination (Ch. Roux, pers. comm.). Nevertheless, the results from the investigated sequences of the other specimens in this article, as well as those in Kemler *et al.* (2006), confirm the proposal that *Microbotryum* should be restricted to the group of anthericolous species on Caryophyllaceae. On the basis of our current knowledge the seed-destroying species on Caryophyllaceae should not be treated as species of either *Ustilago* or *Microbotryum*, as they have been traditionally and in many

recent literature sources (cfr Vánky 1994, 1998), but as members of either *Haradaea* or *Baubinus* (Denchev *et al.* in press). Definitive assignments, though, must await further molecular and/or ultrastructural investigations.

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